

USING AI TO CREATE NEW CHANNELS OF CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT

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Cite This Article: Deepika Sihmar, "Using AI to Create New Channels of Customer Engagement", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 5, Issue 1, Page Number 221-227, 2019.

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Abstract:

Customer engagement has attained a prominent place in the customer-centric marketing approach and has been recognized as a key research priority. Customer engagement involves interacting with customers through a variety of channels in order to strengthen the bond between company and its customers. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is turning out to be a key technology used by companies to engage with their customers. Companies can meet the expectations of customers in a better way by employing AI in every aspect of customer journey. AI is transforming the markets and helping marketers gain a far better knowledge of their consumers, brands, and market segments, as well as in designing and improving consumer experiences to better engage with them. The present chapter has focused on the role of AI in customer engagement, AI technologies used for customer engagement, the challenges of employing AI in customer engagement and the future of AI in customer engagement.

Key Words: Artificial Intelligence, Customer Engagement, Technology, Customer

1. Introduction:

A plethora of techniques are being adopted by companies today to develop and strengthen the bond with their customers due to increased competition, technological advancements, and changing customer-brand relationships (Venkatesan, 2017). While the technological developments have provided the customers a variety of ways to engage with brands and businesses, they have also allowed businesses to automate their interactions with customers. Technology can be integrated into any step of the marketing process to improve customer engagement with brands (Hollebeek et al, 2014). Artificial Intelligence (AI) is quickly becoming a powerful tool for brands and marketers (Vega et al, 2018). Artificial intelligence is defined as "programs, algorithms, systems or machines that demonstrate intelligence" (Shankar, 2018). AI is generating a profound change in customer engagement today. Big giants like Facebook, IBM, Microsoft, Google and Amazon have heavily invested to gain a competitive first-mover advantage. Developing AI-powered experiences that seem like natural human interactions is the new era companies are entering into, thanks to the fact that AI systems can see, talk, and hear. In comparison with computer-assisted automation, AI offers a number of benefits, including the ability to understand which pieces of the data are the most predictive. It has the ability to evolve on its own, based on new knowledge or via trial and error. All of this might happen at a scale beyond a person's envision. AI-driven automated tools can turn data from various distinct sources into meaningful insights by employing advanced business intelligence (Datta, 2018). AI helps to "interpret external data correctly, learn from such data, and exhibit flexible adaptation" (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019).

AI technology assists the companies by predicting customer's future steps and optimizing the customer journey by merging consumer data with AI concepts such as machine learning. Marketers can map each stage of the customer experience and grasp valuable opportunities to engage with them using AI-driven tools that use various data sources. It enables companies to discover existing customer experience gaps, extract pertinent insights, and take the required steps to retain customers and keep them engaged with the brand. AI can also help the companies to build unique and appropriate offers automatically to the right customers at the right moment, enabled by real-time data. By evaluating user data and assisting marketers in making sense of user intent, AI also supports marketers in deciphering the ever-changing world of content marketing.

2. Concept of Customer Engagement:

Participation in and connection with an organization's offerings or value co-creation to active collaboration. Customer engagement is defined as the "intensity of an individual's organization and a customer which can vary from a simple purchase action to word of mouth and referrals to Simply interpreting the term customer engagement, it can be looked upon as a two-way interaction between an organizational activities, which either the dependent psychological state, characterized by a specific intensity level that plays a central role in the process customer or the organization initiates" (Vivek et al, 2012). Customer engagement represents "a highly context of relational exchange" (Fernandes & Esteves, 2016). The customer-brand relationships which were earlier only confined to customer purchases have moved a step further enabled by increased customer awareness and technological advancements to influence satisfaction level as well as foster emotional connection

with the customers, paving the way of engaging the customers with the brand (Kumar & Pansari, 2016). With the huge proliferation of the brands in the marketplace, customers come across numerous brands on a daily basis, however there are only certain brands with which they develop an intense emotional connection and form strong customer-brand relationships (Carvalho & Fernandes, 2018). Customer engagement fosters an emotional connection between a brand and a customer since customers are the ones who choose to engage with a brand among many overwhelming options (Pansari & Kumar, 2017). Customer engagement can be described as a significant tool for developing as well as improving relationships with customers (Brodie et al, 2013). Owing to its significance in customer management, customer engagement behaviors are becoming increasingly important for an organization to affect attitudinal and behavioral loyalty of the customers (Prentice et al, 2018), to enhance its profitability (Harmeling et al, 2017), and for using it as a tool to gain competitive advantage (Kumar et al 2010; Ostrom et al, 2015; Kumar & Pansari, 2016). Engaged customers are advantageous to the organizations in the sense that they are less sensitive to price changes, avoid switching to the competitors, contribute in service development and make referrals (Roy et al, 2018).

3. The Need for Artificial Intelligence in Customer Engagement - The Changing Face of Customer Service:

"AI can engage customers, before and after the sale" (Davenport et al, 2019). In an era of increase in customer touch points as a result of physical-digital blur, companies are struggling with increasing customer expectations which are multiplying day by day. Companies must find a means to enhance the scope, number, and quality of customer service interactions in order to fulfill the escalating demands and compete successfully. The role and function of customer service must be reconsidered by businesses. AI has been employed in customer service to increase internal efficiencies and drive self-service in recent years. Companies can save costs while providing integrated, better, and full consumer experiences by embracing AI's emerging capabilities, which range from video processing to machine learning. To compete successfully, companies are attempting to create integrated and contextually relevant customer service experiences through an extended network of platforms and devices as the real world becomes increasingly digital with wearable gadgets, smart objects, and augmented experiences. Retailers have been extending the amount of communication channels to engage with their customers ranging from traditional communication channels like phone and email to connecting through social networking sites. Communication channels with brands based on perceived convenience, quality, and responsiveness. Delivering Consumers establish their own individual preferences for communicating with retailers by selecting primarily on human assistance. In such a situation, AI offers an easy solution. Also, creating and executing timely and quality assistance becomes increasingly difficult across more channels, especially when depending on pleasant consumer experiences across all communications is a complex and costly endeavor. Human resource expenses can cease growing with easily available AI-powered solutions while saving time and increasing brand automate fast replies will emerge as the new winners. Retailers must use AI to better serve their customers in loyalty by focusing solely on the most complex client concerns. Retailers who embrace AI technologies in order to stay ahead of the curve.

4. How Artificial Intelligence Helps in Better Customer Engagement?

Personalized marketing Personalization deepens the relationship between customer and brand, and fosters customer engagement behavior (Kumar et al, 2019). Personalization may be a challenging and time-consuming endeavor, but AI makes it easier to understand customers and deliver customized offers accordingly (Morgan, 2019). Instead of grouping people into broad groups, AI-based personalization attempts to create optimal customer experiences in real time, tailored particularly to that individual's needs. By analyzing a customer's previous purchases and preferences, AI technology can personalize services and product recommendations leading to better automation, cost savings, increased flexibility, and improved client interactions (Ameen et al, 2018). Booking.com's approach, for example, of personalizing the customer experience with machine learning and deep learning is an instance of how a digital travel company is using AI-driven personalized engagement marketing. Booking.com analyzes the search query entered by the traveler, estimates the user's reaction to various types of accommodations, private homes or hotels and recommends the next destination that the user may like to visit. Several brands have been making use of AI in delivering personalized marketing to engage with the customers, for example, Thread, a UK based fashion company employs AI to deliver individualized apparel recommendations to each customer by collecting information about their personal style in style quizzes; Hilton Hotels uses AI robot to greet their guests and providing answers to their queries; Under Armour, American based sports equipment company uses AI to make personalized health recommendations serving as a personal trainer; Rare Carat, a diamond website, uses AI to assess diamond prices across many vendors to get the best value for each buyer (Morgan, 2019).

Apart from providing personalized recommendations, companies have been leveraging the tool of AI to send personalized advertisements to customers, for example, O2, a UK based telecommunication provider creates over 1,000 different versions of its video commercials with messaging that changes in real time based on the user's device and location; personalized emails, Tripadvisor, for example, uses AI to send curated emails by predicting interesting destinations based on user data from prior vacations and site surfing; personalized

messaging, Starbucks, for instance, employ predictive analytics to send effective, tailored messages to deliver through its application, such as greetings and cross-sells; personalized website experience where AI can present the best-fitting offers and content by assessing hundreds of data points on a single user (including location, demographics, device, website engagement, and so on) (Karlson, 2017). Tailored email marketing campaigns can be swiftly carried out by the companies by using AI-powered tools which can handle customization in the email text. Customer engagement may be boosted by using AI to make your widely disseminated generic email feel more personal.

4.1 Better Customer Experience:

Marbach et al (2016) assert that managers today are increasingly concerned with the ways of engaging customers with the brands in a better way in relation to their competitors and providing them favorable customer experiences. Companies are discovering considerable competitive advantage in their capacity to harness information from data to supplement sales and expedite the company's capacity to enhance employees' performance and the customer experience, thanks to the unparalleled speed of AI invention and adoption. AI has the potential to predict customer behavior by continuously learning and improving from the data it analyzes, enabling the businesses to deliver highly relevant information, enhance sales prospects, and improve the customer experience. AI has the potential to help companies interact with customers on a more personal level in this way, resulting in increased loyalty and trust. To provide genuinely exceptional customer experiences, all customer-focused business units, such as sales, customer support, and marketing, must collaborate and effectively employ AI technologies to achieve shared goals. Companies can use AI to enhance customer experience as they can have better insight into customer needs and improved customer interactions through increased automation. Many companies have been employing AI to provide better customer experiences, Alibaba, the retail giant, for instance, launched a physical "FashionAI" store in Hong Kong with the purpose of using AI to streamline the fashion retail experience wherein intelligent garment tags identify when an item is touched in the store, and smart mirrors show apparel information and propose complementing products. In another instance, The AI-powered BMW Intelligent Personal Assistant allows users to converse and interact with the car directly, and allows the automobile to be operated, functions accessed, and information collected only by voice command providing a unique customer experience. Brick and mortar stores have also been embracing AI to provide enhanced in-store buying experiences. Customers are charged on their Amazon accounts based on the digital footprint of their purchases at the Amazon Go shops, for example, which use AI-powered tracking and monitoring technologies to allow cashier-less grocery stores (Srivastava et al, 2018).

5. AI Technologies Utilized for Customer Engagement:

AI's integration into various marketing processes is creating numerous opportunities for marketers. According to Kumar et al (2016), AI-enabled technology can be a significant source of competitive advantage for businesses engagement. The accuracy of consumer preference forecasts can be enhanced through AI, hence enhancing the Marketers have been incorporating various tools of AI into their functioning to create better customer value provided by the company to consumers throughout the course of their relationship (Kumar et al, 2019)

5.1 Chat Bots:

Intelligence (AI) technology and AI-powered chatbots will be a key component in supporting the next "By 2025, as many as 95 percent of all customer interactions will be through channels supported by artificial generation of customer experience" (Microsoft, 2017). AI-enabled chatbots are becoming increasingly popular because of their beneficial influence across a wide range of businesses. These chatbots may start conversations with customers and provide appropriate answers to their concerns, as well as assist with every touch point across the customer life cycle and purchase process. Chatbots are comparable to virtual digital assistants, but they're also known as "conversational agents" since they're designed to engage and communicate with actual people via web-based or standalone applications. Businesses may utilize chatbots to enhance engagement metrics by carefully retargeting returning users on their site/app, delivering tailored suggestions, giving connections to useful resources, pushing traffic to key sections of the site, and so on. More brands are moving to AI to better serve their consumers, with Indian giants like Flipkart using AI-powered bots to boost festive sales. Sephora was an early adopter of AI with its chatbot being especially useful for engagement in the cosmetics industry, where the choices may be overwhelming and it's impossible to buy something without first trying it. Levi's also introduced an AI-enabled chatbot to help find the perfect fit where its virtual stylist uses natural language processing to learn about each customer's lifestyle and fit preferences. In another instance, Dominos uses a chatbot to make the ordering process between customers and restaurants go more smoothly in addition to offering interesting and transparent communication along with increased convenience, thus leading to better engagement with the customers. AI chatbots aren't just used by companies as a customer support tool now but also help in the content marketing requirements as well by engaging the customers through fun and suitable content, for example, National Geographic created the Einstein bot a few years ago which was designed to mimic Albert Einstein's speech patterns to generate interest in their new show. The bot wherein users had the option to learn more about the famous scientist and ask him any questions they had (Marr, 2019a).

5.2 Virtual Assistant:

Traditional chatbots are being upgraded to advanced virtual assistants due to rapid technological breakthroughs. Virtual assistants are increasingly attaining prominence in providing better customer experience and keeping them engaged. Virtual assistants are software agents that follow voice or written orders to do human-like tasks. They can be found on any internet-connected device, including smartphones, desktop computers, and in-home speakers. The fast spread of virtual assistants (Apple's Siri, Google Assistant, Microsoft's Cortana and Amazon's Alexa) in both the industry and at home has resulted in a customer engagement revolution. Combining digital assistants with other AI technologies has the potential to transform businesses by making the 2019). As the customers are becoming more accustomed to virtual assistants in their homes and office, they process more efficient, automating complicated activities, and improving customer engagement (Brill et al. instance, virtual assistant is used by SEB, a Swedish Bank to manage natural language conversations, replying potential to change the way companies connect with their customers by allowing them to serve themselves for expect the same from the companies with whom they connect and engage. Smart virtual assistants have the to customer queries related to opening of account or making payments. One of the most appealing features of virtual assistants is their capacity to simplify the client experience. Customers can get real-time help from their digital assistants while doing other things from the comfort of their own home, for example, Marks and Spencer, intervention (Marr, 2019a). Virtual assistants are an excellent illustration of how AI empowers companies to build human-centric consumer experience. Companies may personalize the tone of their virtual assistant, which makes communication with voice technology feel like a real interaction leading to bringing clients closer to their a UK based retailer uses virtual digital assistant to solve 70 per cent of customers' issues without any human in better comprehending callers' moods. It helps employees understand their own attitude by giving brand in a genuine way. MetLife, for example, uses AI-enabled voice analytics technologies to assist call center feedback on when they seem fatigued or irritable, allowing them to change their tone and give more platform. Amazon's Alexa, for example, works with a wide range of third-party devices, from Fitbits and laptops effective and humane customer service. In addition, virtual assistants may work with any other type of digital to camera systems and thermostats, enabling the customers to utilize these gadgets in novel ways.

5.3 Facial Recognition:

Recently, facial recognition technology has elevated the procedure of getting insights into knowing customer preferences to a whole new level. It makes it easier to sell as well as to purchase in situations where Facial Recognition is a type of biometric software that maps and saves an individual's facial traits as a face print. The customer is faced with a difficult decision or is simply unaware of all the features of multiple similar items. Expedia, a well-known tour operator, has teamed up with a Hawaii-based tourist agency, for instance, to deliver face recognition-recommended tour alternatives by assessing which of the Hawaii-based tourism activities featured on the Expedia website connects with the viewer the most positively. Facial recognition can enhance the customer experience by providing personalized and customer-centric services. CaliBurger, a Californian burger establishment, for instance, has lock screen uses facial recology in its kiosks wherein customers scan their faces while in the shop, and the kiosk screen uses facial recognition to display their reward programme, including previous and favorite purchases, allowing the retailer to expedite the ordering process while maintaining a low manpower need. Brands have been using facial recognition to improve in-store customer service, for instance, Walmart has patented a technology that uses AI-based algorithms to identify consumers' facial expressions in checkout queues in order to calculate the service satisfaction score aiding them in improving shopper happiness and in-store experience; for customers flying from the United States, British Airways has implemented biometric facial recognition by which passengers can have their faces scanned by a camera to have their identity validated and board their plane without displaying their passport or boarding card. Emotion analytics

5.4 Natural Language Processing (NLP):

Logs, and forum responses are becoming increasingly important. Natural Language Processing (NLP) is an AI- based technology that aids computers in comprehending, interpreting, and manipulating human language. AI As consumers spend more time online, high-quality natural language processing on social media postings, chatuses natural language to make communication between people and robots smoother (Pantano & Pizzi, 2018), Customers are increasingly expressing their demands, opinions, preferences, and grievances online, and companies can benefit from NLP. NLP can easily translate search terms into something a computer cancomprehend, allowing it to analyze data appropriately, for example, once you start typing, Google not only predicts what popular searches would apply to your inquiry, but it also looks at the big picture and detects what for instance, use AI to forecast what customers would like to buy with help of NLP and produce product you're trying to express rather than the precise search terms. Alibaba, the world's largest ecommerce platform, descriptions for the website (Marr, 2019b).

6. Challenges of Employing Artificial Intelligence in Facilitating Customer Engagement:

To get the most out of AI capabilities, the companies need a well-developed, well-equipped, and well-connected data ecosystem which means that businesses need to invest enormously to interpret data and find

methods to turn it into useful insights (Kumar et al, 2019). When the data is scarce, it might be difficult to get accurate results out of AI-enabled systems. AI relies on high-quality data to function. The AI software will produce bad results if there is insufficient data or data of low quality. Data management will be critical for adopting an efficient AI strategy and ensuring that your data is accurate, dependable, and safe. Further, human prejudices might be pushed into AI systems as part of the data, resulting in biased output. With advancement in AI technology, there is a clear risk of rising technical debt and complexity as businesses might focus on today's needs. Instead, the companies are required to build an architecture that allows technology to be readily integrated into end-to-end processes, allowing data to be transformed into actionable insights and forecasts (Meakin et al, 2018). The success of AI-enabled systems depends upon active engagement of all employees in AI development and not just technical expertise, in order to ensure better operational efficiency. Also, for AI programmes to be successful, they must be linked with clear firm goals implying that AI must essentially be a company-wide endeavor spanning hierarchies, functions, and stakeholders. Because AI technology is continually evolving, businesses must see AI transformations as continuous rather than one-time endeavors. Furthermore, complex software and high-performance hardware are required for AI technology, which is costly to implement and maintain. Smaller firms may have been unable to take use of AI technology in the past due to the high investment required. However, with a rising number of inexpensive AI providers, businesses no longer have to rely on in-house AI development. Another challenge in employing AI to facilitate engagement relates to consumers feeling exploited in data collection experiences due to a lack of understanding of AI's operational criteria, despite AI's capacity to forecast and match preferences (Puntoni et al, 2018). Consumers are also not sure of how their information is being used by companies, even when they share on their will. If the AI application is implemented in a robot, the uneasiness with using AI by customers might get amplified which may lead to adoption problems.

7. The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Customer Engagement:

With a constant growth in technology-enabled customer-brand interactions, several researchers and practitioners have identified many possibilities for organizations to employ artificial AI to boost customer engagement further in the future. Also, the pressure on businesses to use AI was already building prior to the COVID-19 crisis (Cheatham et al, 2018). Many firms are now utilizing AI to swiftly manage the massive difficulties they confront and define a new route for their personnel, customers, and investors in an unpredictable, constantly changing world, owing to the COVID-19 crisis. Companies can make use of combination of live as well as stored data sources of customer relationship management using AI-enabled information processing which might allow businesses to spot patterns in customer engagement behavior and find out which product aspect is relatively more important for customer engagement (Vega et al, 2018). AI can aid the companies to monitor how well their social media is performing. AI-enabled systems can help the marketers build content distribution strategies by collecting and evaluating data regarding the customers. AI might also make it easier for businesses to monitor online customer engagement behaviors in real time. Further, the companies can improve service quality with AI-enabled real time monitoring and find out the functional areas in which improvement is required to better engage with the customers. The companies may make use of AI to segment consumers depending on their current application or product usage with the aid of real-time user behavior. AI-enabled systems can help in automatic transfer of users among segments as their behavior changes. This can help the companies to recommend relevant content, entice users to return to the app, and resolve their concerns. All of this information gained from AI systems can be utilized to build a robust consumer profile and engage with the consumers in a more targeted, timely, and relevant manner.

8. Conclusion:

AI would help to accelerate the digitization of the customer journey. At each stage in the customer journey, AI may be used to deliver an intelligent, convenient, and informed customer experience. AI will continue to enhance the customer engagement, whether through sales channels, marketing platforms or customer service support in the coming decades. As hyper-connected, intelligent products become more common, customer engagement is becoming more crucial to the brand's relationship with customers as well as the future value a firm can expect from an engaged customer. For brands to ensure successful and proactive interaction with their customers, AI-driven solutions must be used across departments such as sales, marketing, and customer relationship management.

References:

1. Ameen, N., Tarhini, A., Reppel, A., & Anand, A. (2018). Customer experiences in the age of artificial intelligence. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 114, 106548.
2. Brill, T. M., Munoz, L. & Miller, R. J. (2019). Siri, Alexa, and other digital assistants: a study of customer satisfaction with artificial intelligence applications. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 35:1401-1436.
3. Brodie, R. J., Ilic, A., Juric, B., & Hollebeek, L. D. (2013). Consumer engagement in a virtual brand community: An exploratory analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 66:105-114.

4. Carvalho, A., & Fernandes, T. (2018). Understanding customer brand engagement with virtual social communities: A comprehensive model of drivers, outcomes and moderators. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 26:23-37.
5. Cheatham, B., Cosmas, A., Mehta, N., & Shah, D. (2018, May 4). How to build AI with (and for) everyone in your organization Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-analytics/our-insights/how-to-build-ai-with-and-for-everyone-in-your-organization>
6. Davenport, T., Guha, A., Grewal, D., & Bressgott, T. (2019). How artificial intelligence will change the future of marketing. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 48: 1-19.
7. Fernandes, T., & Esteves, F. (2016). Customer engagement and loyalty: A comparative study between service contexts. *Service Marketing Quarterly*, 37:125-139.
8. Harmeling, C. M., Moffett, J. W., Arnold, M. J. & Carlson, B. D. (2017). Toward a theory of customer engagement marketing *Journal of Academy of Marketing Science*, 45: 312-335.
9. Hollebeek, L., Glynn, M., & Brodie, R. (2014). Consumer brand engagement in social media: conceptualization, scale development and validation. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 28(2): 149-165.
10. Huang, M. H., & Rust, R. T. (2018). A strategic framework for artificial intelligence in marketing. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 49:30-50.
11. Kaplan, A., & Haenlein, M. (2019). Siri, Siri, in my hand: Who's the fairest in the land? On the interpretations, Customer Engagement: Changing Landscape of Marketing
12. Karlson, K. (2017, August 13). 8 ways intelligent marketers use artificial intelligence. Retrieved from <https://contentmarketinginstitute.com/2017/08/marketers-use-artificial-intelligence/>
13. Kumar, V, Aksoy, L, Donkers, B., Venkatesan, R., Wiesel, T., & Tillmanns, S. (2010). Undervalued or overvalued customers Capturing total customer engagement value. *Journal of Services Research*, 13:297-310.
14. Kumar, V., Dixit, A, Javalgi, R. R. G., & Dass, M. (2016) Research framework, strategies, and applications of intelligent agent
16. Kumar, V, Rajan, B., Venkatesan, R., & Lecinski, J. (2019). Understanding the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Personalized
15. Kumar, V, & Pansari, A. (2016). Competitive advantage through engagement. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 53:497-514.
15. Technologies (IATs) in marketing *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 44(1), 24-45.
16. Engagement Marketing *California Management Review*, 61(4):135-155.
17. Luo, X, Tong, S., Fang, Z, & Qu, Z. (2019) Frontiers: Machines versus humans: The impact of AI chatbot disclosure on customer purchases. *Marketing Science*, 38(6), 937-947.
18. Marbach J, Lages, C. R., & Nunan, D. (2016). Who are you and what do you value? Investigating the role of personality traits
19. Mar, B. (2019a, February 11) 7+ amazing examples of online chatbots and virtual digital assistants in practice. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 32:502-525 practice/sh-32654370533e
19. Mar (2019b, December 9) The 10 best examples of how companies use artificial intelligence in practice. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bernardmarr/2019/12/09/the-10-best-examples-of-how-companies-use-artificial-intelligence-in-practice/sh-630d16187978>
20. Meakin, T. Palmer, J., Vickers, J., & Sartori V. (2018, April 30). Winning with AI is a state of mind. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-analytics/our-insights/winning-with-ai-is-a-state-of-mind>
21. Microsoft (2017, November 8). Powering the future of the customer experience. Retrieved from <https://news.microsoft.com/europe/features/ai-powering-customer-experience/>
22. Morgan, B. (2019, January 24). The 7 best examples of artificial intelligence to improve personalization. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/blakemorgan/2019/01/24/the-7-best-examples-of-artificial-intelligence-to-improve-personalization/?sh-6e52d14c3c4c>
23. Ostrom, A. L., Parasuraman, A., Bowen, D. E., Patricio, L. & Voss, C. A. (2015). Service research priorities in a rapidly changing context. *Journal of Service Research*, 18:127-159.
24. Pansari, A., & Kumar, V. (2017). Customer engagement: the construct, antecedents, and consequences. *Journal of Academy of Marketing Science*, 45:294-311.
25. Pantano, E., & Pizzi, G. (2018). Forecasting artificial intelligence on online customer assistance: Evidence from chatbot patents analysis. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 55, 102096.
26. Prentice, C., Wang, X. & Lin, X. (2018). An organic approach to customer engagement and loyalty. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 60:1-10.
27. Puntoni, S., Reczek, R. W., Giesler, M., & Botti, S. (2018). Consumers and Artificial Intelligence: An Experiential Perspective. *Journal of Marketing*, 85(1):131-151.
28. Roy, S. K., Shekhar, V., Lassar, W. M. & Chen, T. (2018). Customer engagement behaviors: The role of service convenience, fairness and quality. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 44:293-304.
29. Shankar, V. (2018). How artificial intelligence (AI) is reshaping retailing. *Journal of Retailing*, 94(4), 6-11.

30. Srivastava, V, Kishore, S., &Dhingra D. (2018). Technology and the future of customer experience. In S. Popli, B. Rishi (Ed.).
31. Vega, R. P. Kaartemo, V., Lages, C. R., Razavi, N. B... &Männistö, J. (2018). Reshaping the contexts of online customer engagement behavior via artificial intelligence: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Business Research*, 129: 902-910. Limited. 33. Venkatesan, R. (2017). Executing on a customer engagement strategy. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 45(3), 289-293.
32. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 20:127-145.Vivek, S. D., Beatty, S. E., & Morgan, R. M. (2012). Customer engagement: Exploring customer relationships beyond purchase